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Abstract

For hundreds of years, common transactions of money were made based on physical assets like gold, silver, plate, or cash, but in recent years, financial flows have changed significantly and one of these areas has been the Eurozone, a region with 20 countries in Europe that have adopted the Euro as general currency and that have faced a notable shift from traditional cash payments to digital methods. This study analyzes financial flows and their methods of payments in the Eurozone between 2019 and 2023, examining changes on payment and transactions preferences mainly among consumers and businesses thanks to available data based on surveys about payment behaviors around digital and physical methods but also this study analyses digital payments based on the Eurosystem of the European Central Bank (ECB), this research explores trends in cash usage, digital transactions, and the growing role of electronic payment systems.

The findings show a significant decrease in cash transactions, which now represent a smaller share of total payment, and digital methods, such as credit transfers, e-money, and card payments, have grown in terms of percentage and importance, particularly in online and point-of-sale transactions. Additionally, businesses show a clear preference for digital payments due to increased efficiency, security, and consumer demand. However, cash remains relevant for person-to-person transactions and in specific regions with lower digital adoption.

Applying clustering techniques like KNN and the analysis of the different charts show that the eurozone has two different velocities in terms of the adoption of new technologies to make payments, while most of the Western and Northern countries have been adopting different methods of digital payments, central and Mediterranean countries face lags in terms of digitalization, leaning more toward cash transactions.

In terms of predictions, the future financial flow trends reveal that digital payments will continue to expand while cash usage will persist in certain segments. These understandings are crucial for policymakers, financial institutions, and businesses seeking to adapt to an evolving payment landscape and ensure inclusive financial accessibility.

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List of Abbreviations

SPACE	Study on payment attitudes of consumers in the euro area
USD	Dollar of the United States
IT	Information Technology
Amex	American Express
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Customer
B2G	Business to Government
C2B	Customer to Business
C2C	Customer to Customer
C2G	Customer to Government
G2C	Government to Customer
G2B	Government to Business
P2P	Person to Person
SEPA	Single Euro Payments Area
ECB	European central bank
POS	Point of Sale

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1. Introduction

Nowadays is highly probably that you or someone that you know has used cash, debit card, credit card, or an electronic wallet to purchase a coffee, pay your bills, transfer money to a friend, or even receive a salary at the end of the month, methods that are now customary and that permit a dynamic economy permitting a constant movement of financial flows in a large gamma of physical and digital methods. Physical methods like cash in a currency like Dollar, Euro, Yen, Yuan or peso or a digital method using card, electronic money, or even virtual currency like bitcoin, something that is naturally part of the economies of the market.

According to The Global Payments Report, in 2023 the total cash share (In all segments) represents 16% of global transactions value with an estimated 6 trillion USD, and nearly 80% were related to digital wallets, credit cards and debit cards, where even the debit and credit card that have been the most common digital methods to pay, now are not in the first place(The Global Payments Report, 2023)

This is connected to a Study on payment attitudes of consumers in the euro area (SPACE) in 2022 where people made transactions in cash of 59% representing 20% less compared to 2016 when transaction in cash was 79% in the eurozone, this effect is not only due to the pandemic that may have driven financial flows, this has been an ongoing trend that highlights the importance of analyzing money flows. (Zamora-Pérez, Marini and Honkkila, 2024)

furthermore, the International Center of Law and Economics indicates that on the side of business, there is evidence that a business with electronic payment methods increases the cost-effectiveness compared to cash due to consumers tending to spend more money, dynamizing moew the economy and showing a potential way to increase of financial flows (*The Cost of Payments: A Review*, no date)

For all this, the present paper focuses on the analysis of financial flows like the methods of payments in the number of transactions and value of transactions but also its impact in terms of impact in purchases or sales in companies or institutions in countries of the eurozone in recent years.

2. Literature review

Since thousands of years ago, the exchange of goods and services has been a natural behavior of humans, which is constantly generating a shaping of the world in diverse ways like social, economic, cultural and other broad areas. This exchange began as an exchange of goods due to the necessity or desire of people to have the products of others due to the necessity of diversifying its consumption, and it was evolving until the current sophisticated and useful financial system that permitted the exchange through a monetary system which uses money that is accepted for the people in a determined area.

Although this investigation will not go into economic theory in depth, it is necessary to understand that money as a system of value that permits the exchange of goods and services through called “financial transactions” thanks to a general acceptance of society of money due to different characteristics like the reliability (Britannica Money, 2024)

It is pertinent to say that money and its ecosystem were not always as we know it nowadays in the different currencies of each country, it started as an asset or commodity that works as a medium of exchange that for a period of time was defined as an asset that should have some characteristics like portable, indestructible, uniform, cognizable, divisible, malleable, useful like the silver plate, gold or even salt that after centuries of the dominance of commodities, this had an evolution to physical currency as US Dolar, Euro, Yen, Yuan or Peso.(Murad, 1943)

Until this point, all **financial flows** have been conducted with physical instruments like gold or currency that work under and controlled system where the central banks and the traditional bank were in charge of all the physical productions and manual transactional processes and the naturality of the transaction was indeed physical.

But what exactly constitutes a "financial flow"? Eurostat, the statistical office of the European Union, provides a more precise definition referring to the movement of money or financial assets across different economic entities, such as individuals, businesses, and governments which is a basic behavior that is shaping constantly the world. (Eurostata, 2024)

During the last decades, in part of the last technological revolution, these flows have had a transformation into digital, not only in terms of account but also in methods of payment starting with credit and debit cards backed by companies such as Visa, Master Card and

American Express and continue to the internet banks and mobile banks creating a dynamic and competitive sector where the consumer (people, companies or public institutions) decide which method fits better to make a transaction or payment, in cash or digital. Nowadays it is so palpable that we not only find options of traditional banks but also IT companies like Apple Pay, PayPal, Google Pay, payment Networks of franchises like Visa, Master Card or Amex or the new call Neobanks like Nubank, Revolut or N26 that in most of the cases are cheaper than a traditional bank thanks to its cost structure (Henningsson and Hedman, 2014)

Having recognized the changes in financial flows methods and the new market entrants, it is appropriate to talk about the information that comes with it, especially with the digitalization of payments and transaction methods. Now we are facing a wide field and areas of applications like data analysis thanks to a big range of useful data that brings the digitalization of the things (useful data that means data that is traceable, measurable and useable) where a McKinsey Global Survey on digital transformation estimates that 80% of organizations have undertaken large-scale initiatives to adopt digitalization (McKinsey, 2018)

One of the applications is the classifications of consumers due to particular characteristics of each like origin, legal status, financial behavior, something that have being adopted nowadays by the government, statistical institutions, companies and banks and financial entities making also classification or clustering of all the clients* and users*) to have a better analysis and understanding of each player and give better experience or solutions according to its necessity to the consumers, for that there are segments like:

- People (sometimes according to the necessity is sub-segmented according to the revenues, age)
- Companies (also according to the necessity is sub-segmented according to the revenues, sector, and number of employees)
- Government (also according to the necessity is sub-segmented according to the size of the annual budget, and population)

An example of this technology revolution is met in 2024 with The Laboratory for AI-Powered Financial Technologies Limited (AIFT) an innovative research and technology center of City University of Hong Kong and Columbia University showing Clustering Techniques with machine learning demonstrating the current use of classification with big data provides financial institutions and technology companies capacity to personalize financial services to customers and users improving its experience. (Hongzong, 2024)

This is also evidenced by the current projects of different commercial banks around the world, for example:

- ✓ Citibank for example won in 2023 and also for the last 22 years named World's Best Digital Bank 2023 by Global Finance Magazine thanks to utilizing big data technology to analyze customer information segmenting customer groups offering different solutions to meet customer needs.(Citigroup, 2023)
- ✓ Banks like Wells Fargo Bank set up investment portfolios for the clients it serves by building intelligent advisory platforms that allow for active technology integration(Arnott, 2023)

As can be seen, digitalization brings opportunities to accurately analyze and interpret data, thus allowing companies and financial institutions to know the trends given the preferences of their clients and where there are opportunities to improve.

Recently there are new models that classify and analyze commercial transactions (financial flows) among the parties involved to identify opportunities and make better decisions (Chen, 2024). One of the most knowledgeable is focusing on electronic commerce due to its natural facility to have data even in real time where the main classifications are:

- Business to Business (B2B)
- Business to Customer (B2C)
- Business to Government (B2G)
- Customer to Business (C2B)
- Customer to Customer (C2C)
- Customer to Government (C2G)
- Government to Customer (G2C)
- Government to Business (G2B)

It's important to clarify the current classification of individuals because customer or client behavior today contrasts greatly depending on who they're interacting with. There are also several technical factors playing, one of the most significant being how information is presented on many websites, such as those of central banks. Typically, this information is displayed separately according to the cluster or segments, making it necessary to adopt these characteristics from now on.

So far, we have known that today there are multiple methods to realize **payments** and **transactions** but also how the new digital methods bring new wide possibilities of analysis however, how has the behavior been in the last years?

Based on research made by Study on payment attitudes of consumers (segment of people) in the euro area (SPACE) people made transactions in cash where in 2022 59% of people use cash as a method of payment representing 20% less compared to 2016 where the transaction in cash was 79% in the eurozone, this effect is not only due to the pandemic that may have driven financial flows, this has been an ongoing trend that highlights the importance of analyzing money flows. (Zamora-Pérez, Marini and Honkkila, 2024)

Method of payment			
User	2016	2019	2022
Cash	79%	72%	59%
Digital	21%	28%	41%
Mix*			74%
Mix*: At least one transaction in cash on the year			

Table 2.1 Method of Payment Consumers 2016 - 2022

According to The Global Payments Report, in 2023 the cash share represents 16% of global transactions value (all segments) with an estimated of 6 trillion of USD, and near 80% were digitally related to credit transfer, direct debit, digital wallets, credit cards and debit cards. One characteristic is that in terms of the value of transactions, digital methods like debit and credit cards for a moment were the most common digital methods to pay, now are not in the first place(The Global Payments Report, 2023)

All of this is part of financial flows showing a new comportment of Business, people and government, changing traditional methods of payments and transactions and becoming more digital or at least diversifying its comportment due to different good aspects or benefits.

But why is important a world with multiple methods of transactions? There are some reasons, for example, according to Forbes, having multiple payment methods gives a better experience to customers who typically expect fewer choices, allowing them to select their preferred payment method making a purchase more convenient and enjoyable increases the likelihood of customers returning for future purchases.(Koksal, 2019) and other reasons we could find:

- **Security:** Reduces the risk of physical theft, a particularly relevant benefit in countries or regions with high levels of insecurity. (Koksal, 2019)
- **Accessibility and Convenience:** Facilitates users can have a better performance anytime and anywhere, reducing the limitations that face country side area
- **E-commerce:** Increase the possible potential customer base, which also increases potential revenues (Koksal, 2019)
- **Easy portability:** Can be accessed and used conveniently through a cellphone or other mobile devices or devices with internet
- **Easier Traceable operation:** Provides users detailed information about all transactional movements like: expenses, revenues, and even debts, ensuring greater financial transparency.
- **Increase of taxes:** Digital transactions leave a transactional footprint that permits each money flow to be accurately tracked, allowing Taxes institutions an easier tax collection and avoiding evasion.
- **Easier to Audit:** This allows companies and governments to track and understand financial flows more effectively, providing third parties with the option to inspect when needed.
- **Time Efficiency:** Allows users to make payments and transactions without visiting a physical bank or being physically close to the recipient. It also enables international transactions and supports multitasking through advanced banking features, such as handling payroll efficiently.
- **Reduce of cost for payments***:** Although many of the transactions generate a cost either by the franchise or by the bank itself, on many occasions when there are large amounts of money, the company must pay to the bank for its recollection due to insecurity of transport it and this service has a cost.
- **Banks knowledge:** Permits to banks and financial institutions have information of its financial flows that could create potential future loans.
- **Increase potential sales:** Offering multiple digital payment options makes it easier for consumers to access and use their funds or loans, encouraging more purchases. (GlobalPayments, 2023)

Everything mentioned aligns with a World Bank report, which shows that between 2017 and 2020 the annual number of cashless (or digital) businesses rose from 91 to 135 transactions per person, which also show a tendency to a world with a variety of methods of payments,

tendency especially high in countries with high income as eurozone countries where the rose in the same period of years was from 316 to 371 cashless (digital) transactions as shown in the following chart (World Bank Blogs, 2024)

Figure 2.1 Digital Transactions per Capita 2017 – 2020

This is also associated with an inform of European council about E-commerce made in 2023 showing 3 in 4 people buy online with a market of 300 million people purchasing online in the European Union, 22% more compared to 2010 which means that more than 200 million people have used one digital method to do the purchase (It may not have necessarily been done using a digital tool owned by the interested party, as it could have been accessed through a family member’s or friend’s device. However, its use is still considered valid, any way of independent ownership). (European Council, 2023)

Figure 2.2 Percentage of internet users in EU buying online

To understand the key of digital payment methods for today's economies, it is necessary to be aware of the challenges around the use and diversification of payment methods. Having success in diversifying payment options comes with significant challenges, and failure on it can impact in a negative way because economies are heavily dependent on transactions and this failure means lower dynamization.

Key factors that influence the success of payment diversification include:

- Legislation and Regulation of payments systems
- Accessibility
- Know how to use
- Acceptance

Legislation: According to the World Bank countries with high income like the eurozone have in general a better legislative regulatory payment system compared to the rest of the world that permits a better dynamic economy. In this aspect, 97% of the countries have banking law, 86% central bank law, 74% electronic money (e-money) law (or equivalent)

In the specific case of the Eurozone, exist the systemically important payment system (SIPS) in charge of regulation of all financial flows inside the zone and also the international relation and as the institution says they are working to bring an instant payment environment due to "People expect money to move as quickly as emails" (EUR-lex, 2014)

Accessibility: refers to the facility of use for the population, in the words of Kurd Schmid Managing director of Digital Banking "Accessibility in payments means ensuring that everyone, regardless of physical or cognitive abilities, socioeconomic background, or geographic location, can use financial services with ease and confidence" (*Making the payment journey more accessible for all | G+D Spotlight*, 2023) .

But to have accessibility it is necessary to have an infrastructure that supports this, in the case of digital methods it requires a range of elements like electricity, sometimes internet connectivity, and equipment that permit the normal usability of digital payments and transactions like computers, payment gateways like PayPal or Stripe, point of sale terminals, mobile points of sales like Apple pay or Google pay, a payment network that accept different franchises like Visa, Master Card or American Express.

Adoption: This term is related to the acceptance or willingness of people to use a payment mechanism. Although this depends on the availability of the service or tools for the normal

use of the payment method (in other words, that it has the necessary infrastructure and is widely linked to the previous point of accessibility), adoption depends largely on personal choice (preferences) and persistence in their habits as confirmed by a study by the European Central Bank. (Zamora-Pérez, Marini and Honkkila, 2024)

Within this same research, one of the deductions that impact the possible projections in digital adoption is found and it is "cash use remaining persistent among a broad spectrum of the population" concluding that even with a highly advanced financial system and increasing digitalization, many people in the euro area, from various demographic groups, still choose to use cash for their daily transactions, which suggests to us that it is difficult for a 100% digitalized country to exist and that there is also a pivot in the growth curve (Zamora-Pérez, Marini and Honkkila, 2024)

Know how-to-use: Another important point, and no less significant, is the how-to-use. Despite digitalization is in somehow creating to facilitate daily life, it cannot be hidden that there are people, especially older people, who find it difficult to use digital tools. Withdrawing money, paying a bill online or even checking how much money is in their account are tasks that are often complex despite the increasingly easy way of using them. This is clearly a barrier that prevents digitalization and promotes a cash society.

In the Euro Zone case, these topics have been widely developed by the Single Euro Payments Area (SEPA) where developed an integrated and standardized pan-European payments improving the competition and driving innovation that is also answered as better innovation(Zhang *et al.*, 2019)

Furthermore, the European Central Bank is working on a digital Euro, an electronic euro equivalent to cash complementing the banknotes and coins. This payment will be available free of charge to everyone and open a door to unification of payments due to in the eurozone, there is still no single European payment system and 13 out of 20 countries depend exclusively on international scheme.(European Central Bank, 2023)

To summarize, the literature review shows that financial flows have clearly changed over time, shifting from conventional cash-based systems to more varied and digital payment options. This shift has been thanks to different achievements, technological advancements, changing consumer behaviors, regulatory frameworks, etcetera that have been boosted during the last two decades.

It is also relevant to mention that different studies emphasize on benefits of diversified payment systems, such as enhanced accessibility, convenience, and economic efficiency, however, significant challenges remain, including disparities in digital adoption, regulatory inconsistencies, and barriers to accessibility for certain demographic groups, particularly the elderly and those in underdeveloped regions.

Despite these challenges, there is an evident global trend toward the diversification of methods that also could be called digitalization, as shown by the growth of card use, digital wallets, mobile payments, and instant transfers. But it is necessary to clarify the persistence existing of cash usage in many regions, including parts of the Eurozone, suggesting a complete transition to digital payments is still far from the reality.

This literature review show the importance of understanding both the technological and human factors that influence payment method adoption. It also shows gaps in the current research, particularly regarding the impact of digital payments on financial inclusion and economic dynamism. Therefore, this literature review aims to investigate these areas further, focusing on the diversification of payment methods and their socio-economic implications in the Eurozone.

3. Research methodology

3.1. Research Design:

This work applies a mixed-methods research design to achieve an overall analysis and prediction of financial flows in the Eurozone, an area with 20 countries of the European Union that have adopted the euro as the single currency, despite there are more countries with the use of euro as currency like Montenegro, it is not officially accepted by the European central bank (ECB) what this means the non-printing of money. (European Commission, 2025)

- Why the Eurozone and not the European Union?

As it was explained before Eurozone is a region with a single official currency which means that the devaluation or revaluation of the money affects all the countries in the same way, and this characteristic in particular makes the analysis easier and better due to the effect in terms of inflations, purchasing power and other characteristics can affect people's decisions.

Decisions that have a wide range of impacts for people, companies, financial institutions and even government, for example, can influence the velocity of digitalization of payments due to the loss of value of the money or even lack of cash. It is vital to clarify that inflation is not only affected by the fluctuations in money exchange but also by different characteristics like oscillations in the price of energy, salaries, price of houses and in general all of the products and services of an economy.

This analysis and prediction of financial flows is specifically focused on the mechanisms or methods that the population uses to complete payments or transactions of money in a mix, of physical and digital methods of payments.

physical methods:

- **Cash:** Banknotes and coins that are carried out at the time and in person

Mixed methods:

- **Cheques:** A written order from one party (the drawer) to another (the drawee; normally a credit institution) requiring the drawee to pay a specified sum on demand to the drawer or a third party specified by the drawer. (Cambridge English Dictionary, 2025)

- **Remittances:** money that people send or receive to or from another country.

and particularly digital methods such:

- **Credit transfer:** A payment method where a payer instructs their payment service provider to transfer funds directly to a beneficiary's account. (*Credit transfers | ECB Data Portal, 2025*)
- **Direct Debits:** A payment that occurs when someone let a company take money directly from his or her bank account to pay for things like bills, subscriptions, or for example insurance. (Bank, 2024)
- **E-money:** An electronic store of monetary value on a technical device that may be widely used for making payments to entities other than the e-money issuer (*Electronic money | ECB Data Portal, 2025*)
- **Credit and debit card:** A payment through the usage of a debit or credit card to pay for something, whether in a store, online, or at a mobile POS (Point of sale) (Bank, 2019)

To avoid double accounting, it is necessary to first understand in a technical way how financial flows work through the following formulas and examples:

3.1.1. Financial flows in a close economy

First, and for easier understanding, we consider a closed economy, where there is no interaction with other countries or economies. In this case, the Eurozone is considered as a single economy since it is within the same monetary system. How is a closed economy, the total inflows of money that a person, company or institution receives is exactly the same amount of outcome that a person, company or institution sends as an emitter, sender or issuer (In a closed economy there are no remittances)

$$FF_{total} = FF_{inflows} = FF_{outflows}$$

Equation 3.1.1 Total Financial flows in a close economy

FF_{total} : Total of financial flows due to transfer, payments, collection of money, etc.

$FF_{inflows}$: Financial inflows (revenues, incoming transfers, sell transfers).

$FF_{outflows}$: Financial flows outflows (payments, outgoing transfers, buy transfer).

One example is the person X receives:

- Salary of 1000€
- Transfer of a friend of 200€
- Transfer for a sale of a phone for 100€

So, in this case,

$$FF_{inflows} = 1000€ + 200€ + 100€ = 1300€$$

If we look at it from an output perspective, there is:

- Salary paid for the company of 1000€
- An output of his friend that sent 200€
- Transfer for the purchase of a third party for 100€

$$FF_{outflows} = 1000€ + 200€ + 100€ = 1300€$$

This is relevant due to the further analysis should be based only on output or income of money, Otherwise, it would not be practical, and it would not be clear since we are **duplicating the information**.

3.1.2. Financial Flows in an open economy

Second, in an **open economy**, where countries constantly interact and trade with each other, **remittances** and **investment flows** become key players in shaping the flow of money. These international transactions do not just impact individual families or businesses, they also influence the general balance of money in the economy. When more money flows in from foreign investments and remittances than flows out, it creates a higher demand for the local currency, often leading to its **appreciation**. On the flip side, if more money leaves the country than comes in, the local currency can **devalue**.

This delicate balance between money coming in and going out directly impacts the **exchange rate**, showing just how interconnected economies are today. What happens in one part of the world—whether it's a surge in foreign investments or a wave of remittances can move and influence the power of a country's currency. It's a clear reminder that in our globalized world, no economy operates in isolation.

Therefore, the new formula for financial flows is:

$$FF_{inflows} + (R_{inflows} + |R_{outflows}| + I_{inflows} + |I_{outflows}|) = \\ = FF_{outflows} + (R_{outflows} + |R_{inflows}| + I_{outflows} + |I_{inflows}|)$$

Equation 3.1.2 Financial Flows in an open economy

- Remittances incomes $R_{inflows}$: Refers to remittance inflows, such the money that is sanded to the origin country by individuals working abroad.
- Investment and foreign direct investment incomes $I_{inflows}$: Refers to investment inflows, such as foreign direct investment (FDI) or portfolio investment into the country.
- Remittances outcomes $R_{outflows}$: Refers to remittance outflows, such as money sent by individuals within the country to recipients abroad.
- Investment and foreign direct investment outcomes $I_{outflows}$: Refers to investment outflows, such as capital sent abroad for business expansion or portfolio investment in foreign markets.

Note that some equations within the parentheses are in absolute value, which indicates that their value, despite being opposite to the input of financial flows, for example, the value must be positive since this value is part of the total sum of the financial flows.

3.1.3 Financial Flows in terms of methods of payment

Third, the total of financial flows are the summarize of the flows in the different methods like digital, physical and mix methods.

$$FF_{Total} = FF_{digital} + FF_{physical} + FF_{mix}$$

Equation 3.1.3 Financial flows in terms of methods

$$FF_{digital} = emoney\ payments + Direct\ debits + credit\ transfers + card\ payments$$

$$FF_{physical} = cash$$

$$ff_{mix} = cheques$$

This formula can apply for both input and output of financial flows as is shown in the next formulas.

$$FF_{input} = FF_{input-digital} + FF_{input-physical} + FF_{input-mix}$$

Equation 3.1.4 Financial Flows as inputs

$$FF_{output} = FF_{output-digital} + FF_{output-physical} + FF_{output-mix}$$

Equation 3.1.5 Financial Flows as outputs

and as determined in the first formula, it is known that the total financial flows are equal to the input of the financial flows or the output of the financial flows.

Digital Financial Flows ($FF_{digital}$): Represents all electronic and digital forms of financial transactions. The formula breaks it down into specific subcategories.

- **E-Money Payments:** Payments made through digital money systems like mobile money, online wallets, or digital banking.
- **Direct Debits:** Automated transfers authorized by the payer, commonly used for recurring bills.
- **Credit Transfers:** Payments initiated by the payer to the recipient's bank account (e.g., online or bank transfers).
- **Card Payments:** Payments made using credit or debit cards, including point-of-sale and online transactions.

Physical Financial Flows ($FF_{physical}$): Refers to transactions conducted with physical cash as the medium of exchange.

Mixed Financial Flows (FF_{mix}): represents flows that involve a combination of physical and digital methods. In this case, it is represented by **cheques**, which involve a physical component (the cheque itself) but are processed electronically by banks.

3.2 Primary Data:

The primary data was obtained from three different datasets of the official website of the European Central Bank (ECB), the first is based on survey made to consumers about the attitudes about payments and availability methods of payments in both cash and digital options, the second is based on a survey made to companies where there is information about the accepted methods and preference methods and the third one is based on a complete data transaction of entirely segments about all digital and mix methods, this last data set is not available for cash due to the naturality of the traceability because to it doesn't leave a transactional footprint.

3.2.1 First dataset - segment consumers

This first data set has origin in a **study on payment attitudes of consumers in the euro area** based on a survey made by SPACE updated in December of 2024, survey made to 52.180 people around the 20 countries of Euro zone, this is a representative sample of every country that was made according to share population.

✓ **Location of data set:**

- The dataset 1 can be accessed in the following section:
https://www.ecb.europa.eu/stats/ecb_surveys/space/html/ecb.space2024~19d46f0f17.en.html
- To direct access to the dataset number 1, use this link:
https://www.ecb.europa.eu/stats/ecb_surveys/space/shared/pdf/ecb.space2024_countryspecifiedata.en.xlsx
- The dataset 2 can be accessed in the following section:
https://www.ecb.europa.eu/stats/ecb_surveys/space/html/ecb.space2024~19d46f0f17.en.html

To direct access to the dataset 2, use this link:

https://www.ecb.europa.eu/stats/ecb_surveys/space/shared/pdf/ecb.space2024_charts.en.xlsx

This data set provides understandings into the different concepts like:

- ✓ **Share of Payment Instruments at POS** (segment people): shows the distribution of payment methods used for in-person transactions at physical retail locations (European Central Bank, 2024)
- ✓ **Share of Payment Instruments for P2P Payments** (segment people): Focuses on direct transactions between individuals, such as bank transfers, mobile payment apps, and cash exchanges, assessing trends in peer-to-peer payments. (European Central Bank, 2024)
- ✓ **Share of Payment Instruments for Online Payments** (segment people): Shows the information of digital transactions, including cards, credit transfers, direct debits, instant payments, E-payment solutions and others. (European Central Bank, 2024)

- ✓ **Cash Used at the POS** (segment people): Examines the use of physical currency for in-person transactions at point-of-sale terminals, showing trends in cash payments across different sectors.
- ✓ **Online Payments** (segment people): Focuses on electronic transactions conducted via digital platforms, including card payments, credit transfers, direct debits, instant payments, and e-money solutions used in e-commerce and online services. (European Central Bank, 2024)
- ✓ **P2P Payments** (segment people): Analyzes person-to-person transactions, covering cash exchanges, mobile app payments, credit transfers, and instant payments, reflecting consumer behavior in informal or non-commercial settings. (European Central Bank, 2024)
- ✓ **Payment Instruments Used at the POS** (segment people): Breaks down the payment methods utilized at physical retail locations, such as cash, cards, mobile apps, and alternative methods, providing insights into consumer preferences for in-store purchases. (European Central Bank, 2024)
- ✓ **Payment with Account or Card** (segment people): Differentiates transactions based on whether they were completed using direct bank account access (e.g., credit transfers) or card-based methods, offering a comparative view of account-based and card-based payment behaviors. (European Central Bank, 2024)
- ✓ **POS Transactions Where Cash is Accepted** (segment people): Highlights the proportion of point-of-sale terminals that continue to accept cash payments, reflecting on the accessibility and availability of cash as a payment option in retail environments. (European Central Bank, 2024)
- ✓ **Usage Scenarios** (segment people): Explores the contexts in which various payment methods are employed, categorizing transactions by Point of Sale (POS), Peer-to-Peer (P2P), and Online payments to understand consumer payment preferences across different scenarios. (European Central Bank, 2024)

As outcome, there is data consolidation of every country in the eurozone with the further details:

Category	Magnitude	Item	Meaning
Share of payment instruments at POS	Number and Value	Cash	Physical money used for transactions at points of sale.
		Card	Debit or credit cards used for in-person payments at POS terminals.
		Mobile	Payments made via mobile devices using apps like Apple Pay, Google Pay, or other digital wallets.
		Other	Alternative payment methods used at POS, such as vouchers or loyalty points.
Share of payment instruments used for P2P	Number and Value	Cash	Physical money exchanged directly between individuals.
		Cards and mobile apps	Payments made using credit/debit cards or mobile apps like PayPal, Venmo, or similar peer-to-peer platforms.
		Credit transfers	Bank-to-bank transfers initiated by individuals for personal transactions.
		Instant payments	Real-time bank transfers where funds are transferred and received immediately, commonly used for urgent or direct payments.
Share of payment instruments used for online payments	Number and Value	Cards	Credit or debit cards used for making purchases on websites or online platforms.
		Credit transfers	Direct bank account transfers used for online purchases, often involving an intermediary or payment gateway.
		Direct debits	Automatic withdrawals from a bank account authorized for recurring payments, such as subscriptions or utility bills.

		Instant payments	Real-time digital payments for online transactions, similar to instant bank transfers.
		E-payment solutions	Payment systems like PayPal, Stripe, or other online wallets specifically designed for e-commerce transactions.
		Other	Any other methods used for online payments, including cryptocurrencies or less common payment gateways.
cash used at the POS	Number and Value	2022 vs 2024	Comparison of cash usage at POS between 2022 and 2024 by number and value of transactions.
online payments	number and value	Other	Other online payment methods not categorized, such as cryptocurrencies.
		Cards	Number of online transactions made using credit or debit cards.
		Credit transfers	Number of online transactions done via direct bank transfers.
		Direct debits	Number of online transactions using automatic bank debits.
P2P payments	number and value	Cash	Number of P2P transactions using cards or mobile payment apps.
		Cards and mobile apps	Other P2P payment methods not categorized.
		Other	Number of P2P transactions made via credit transfers.
		Credit transfers	Total value of P2P transactions using cash.
payment instruments used at the POS	number and value	Mobile app	Payments made at POS using mobile payment apps like Apple Pay, Google Pay, or Samsung Pay.
		Cash	Physical currency used directly at the point of sale.

		Other	Alternative payment methods at POS such as vouchers, loyalty points, or gift cards.
		Cards	Debit or credit cards used at POS for in-person transactions.
payment with an account or card	share	account	Share of transactions directly debited from bank accounts without using a card.
		card	Transactions share conducted with debit or credit cards.
POS transactions where cash is accepted	share		Share of POS locations that accept cash as a payment method.
Usage Scenarios	number and value	POS	Number and value of transactions at physical points of sale.
		P2P	Number and value of person-to-person transactions between individuals.
		Online	Number and value of transactions completed online or through e-commerce platforms.

Table 3.1.1 Categorical Data Structure segment People

total data points are distributed according to the next table:

Category	cash used at the POS	online payments	P2P payments	payment instruments used at the POS	payment with an account or card	POS transactions where cash is accepted	Usage Scenarios	Grand Total
Count of year	84	174	48	50	84	84	6	530
Count of Region	84	174	48	50	84	84	6	530
Count of POS							6	6
Count of P2P							6	6
Count of Online							6	6
Count of Mobile app				48				48

Count of 2022 vs 2024	40							40
Count of Cash			48	50				98
Count of Cards and mobile apps			48					48
Count of Other		48	48	50				146
Count of Cards		48		50				98
Count of Credit transfers		48	48					96
Count of Direct debits		48						48
Count of Instant payments		44	44					88
Count of E-payment solutions		48						48
Count of share of cash	42							42
Count of share		122			84	82		288
Total	250	754	332	298	252	250	30	2166

Table 3.1.2 Data Structure segment People

3.2.2 The second dataset – segment companies

(Named as Consolidation_3) as it was mentioned before, is a **study on payment attitudes of consumers in the euro area** based on a survey made by SPACE, this survey was made to 7.574 companies around all the countries with different characteristics to understand better the Eurosystem's retail payments based on companies behavior, accessibility of payments methods and payments preferences updated on December 19, 2024. (Bank, 2024)

These characteristics are based on the sector or economic activity:

- Retail
- Accommodation and food service activities
- Arts, entertainment and recreation

And the size of the company, in this case, the company with the biggest number of employees is 249:

- Micro (0-9 employees)
- Small (10-49 employees)
- Medium (50-249 employees)

As can be seen, large and corporate companies are not included, which partially reduces the survey's reflection of the entire private business sector. As a premise, it is considered that large and corporate companies have many more resources, both

human and financial, and it is expected that these companies have an even greater capacity for digitalization. In addition, it is possible that the amounts for these companies are even higher, and it is expected that due to issues of risk, traceability, and costs, as mentioned in the literature review, these shipments will be made through digital means.

Location of dataset:

- ✓ The dataset can be accessed in the following section:
 - <https://www.ecb.europa.eu/press/blog/date/2023/html/ecb.blog230206~1ea270a762.en.html>
 - To direct access to the dataset number, use this link: https://www.ecb.europa.eu/press/use-of-cash/pdf/ecb.uccea202409_annex.en.xlsx

This data set provides understandings into the number of businesses that accept methods shown in percentage (%) and preferences shown as a share (%) of transactions across different payment scenarios, including:

- ✓ **Accepted and Preferred Payment Methods (segment companies):** Examines the payment methods that companies accept and which one of them prefer to use, around different options like: Cash, Card, Bank cheque, Credit transfer, Direct debit or e-invoice, Gift card or voucher, Online or mobile payment, Crypto-asset or Other method of payment.(Bindseil and Schneeberger, 2023)

As outcome, there is data consolidation of every country in the eurozone with the further details:

Category	Magnitude	Item	Meaning
Accepted and preferred means of payment	Accepted means and preferred means	Cash	Physical money that is widely accepted and preferred for smaller, in-person transactions.
		Card*	Debit or credit cards that are commonly accepted by merchants and preferred by consumers for convenience and ease of use.

	Bank cheque	Written checks issued from a bank account, often used for high-value or formal transactions.
	Credit transfer	Bank transfers used for payment of bills or large transactions, typically accepted by businesses.
	Direct debit or e-invoice	Recurring or automated payments deducted from a bank account, often used for subscriptions or invoices.
	Gift card or voucher	Prepaid cards or vouchers accepted by retailers, often used as gifts or to redeem specific services.
	Online or mobile payment	Digital or mobile payments processed through apps or online platforms, such as Google Pay or Apple Pay.
	Crypto-asset	Cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin or Ethereum, which are accepted by some merchants and preferred by tech-savvy or privacy-conscious consumers.
	Other	Any additional payment methods not categorized above, often context-specific or industry-specific alternatives.

Table 3.1.3 Categorical Data Structure segment companies

In total the data values are distributed according to the next table:

Values	Accepted and preferred means of payment	Share of payment instruments at POS	Share of payment instruments used for online payments	Share of payment instruments used for P2P	Grand Total
Count of Category	42	42	42	42	168

Count of Country	42	42	42	42	168
Count of Mobile-value		42			42
Count of Cards and mobile apps-value				42	42
Count of Credit transfers			42		42
Count of Direct debits			42		42
Count of Instant payments			42	42	84
Count of E-payment solutions			42		42
Count of Cash	42	42		42	126
Count of Card	42	42	42		126
Count of Bank cheque	20				20
Count of Direct debit or e-invoice	21				21
Count of Gift card or voucher	21				21
Count of Online or mobile payment	21				21
Count of Crypto-asset	21				21
Count of Other	42	42	42	42	168
Count of Credit transfer	42			42	84
Count of Direct debit or e-invoice2	21				21
Count of Online or mobile payment2	21				21
Count of Don't know / No answer	21				21
Total	419	252	336	294	1301

Table 3.1.4 Data Structure segment Companies

3.2.3 Data set from the Eurosystem of European Central Bank

Third data set (named consolidation_1) The dataset from the European Central Bank (ECB) is a dataset which collects all traceable payment transactions data from the different digital and mixed methods providing comprehensive ideas into the adoption and usage in terms of number, value, and transaction per capita.

Location

The data was taken specifically, from the 'Data' section and the 'Datasets' subsection, as shown in the following link: <https://data.ecb.europa.eu/data/datasets>" The most recent complete year included in the analysis is 2023. Although the data is updated quarterly and semi-annually in 2024, it was intentionally excluded to maintain consistency and avoid potential confusion in the analysis. Only complete annual data up to 2023 was considered, as the ECB typically updates the datasets six months after the end of each reporting period.

At this point and with the disponible information the criteria for taking the information is:

- ✓ Frequency: a yearly frequency is chosen because behavioral changes in people are not typically observable over short periods, as noted in the previous literature review. This approach is also useful for identifying clear trends in the analysis.
- ✓ Dataset Scope: it was important to identify all possible datasets, as the goal is not only to analyze the Eurozone as a whole but also to examine individual countries separately.
- ✓ Data Consistency: As was mentioned in the research design; to prevent double counting, the decision was made to use data on financial flows specifically related to "sent: from." This approach aligns with the methods people select based on their needs and ensures that the analysis reflects accurate and relevant information.

In consequence, the chosen dataset is:

1. Total euro per capita of cheques, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.CHQ.2._Z.N.EUR_R_POP)
2. Total euro per capita of credit transfers, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.CT0.1._Z.N.EUR_R_POP)
3. Total euro per capita of direct debits, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.DD.2._Z.N.EUR_R_POP)
4. Total euro per capita of e-money payments, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.EMP0.1._Z.N.EUR_R_POP)
5. Total euro per capita of other payment services, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.SER.1._Z.N.EUR_R_POP)
6. Total euro per capita of total payment transactions (incl. cash withdrawals), sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.TOTL.1._Z.N.EUR_R_POP)
7. Total pure number per capita of card payments, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.CP0.1._Z.N.PN_R_POP)
8. Total pure number per capita of total payment transactions (excl. cash withdrawals), sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.TOTL1.1._Z.N.PN_R_POP)
9. Number of cheques - from Euro area (changing composition)
(PSS.A.U2.F000.I35.Z00Z.NT.X0.20.Z0Z.Z)
10. Total number of card payments, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.CP0.1._Z.N.PN)

11. Total number of credit transfers, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.CT0.1._Z.N.PN)
12. Total number of direct debits, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.DD.2._Z.N.PN)
13. Total number of e-money payments, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.EMP0.1._Z.N.PN)
14. Total number of total payment transactions (excl. cash withdrawals), sent - from: euro area (changing composition) (PAY.A.U2.W0.TOTL1.1._Z.N.PN)
15. Total value of card payments, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.CP0.1._Z.N.EUR)
16. Total value of cheques, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.CHQ.2._Z.N.EUR)
17. Total value of credit transfers, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.CT0.1._Z.N.EUR)
18. Total value of direct debits, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.DD.2._Z.N.EUR)
19. Total value of e-money payments, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.EMP0.1._Z.N.EUR)
20. Total value of money remittances, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.MREM.1._Z.N.EUR)
21. Total value of other payment services, sent - from: euro area (changing composition)
(PAY.A.U2.W0.SER.1._Z.N.EUR)
22. Total value of total payment transactions (excl. cash withdrawals), sent - from: euro area (changing composition) (PAY.A.U2.W0.TOTL1.1._Z.N.EUR)
23. Value of total payment transactions (excl. cash withdrawals), sent - from: euro area, to: Rest of the World (PAY.A.U2.W1.TOTL1.1._Z.N.EUR)

In each of the tables there are some codes that are explain in the next table as a summary.

Code Segment	Meaning
PAY	Dataset identifier for payment statistics.
A	Frequency of the data: Annual.

H	Frequency of the data: Semi-Annual.
B0	Reference area: Euro area (EA19).
U2	Reference area: Euro area (EA).
W0	Counterpart area: World (all entities, including reference area, including IO).
W1	Counterpart area: Rest of the world (excluding reference area).
TOTL	Transaction type: Total payment transactions (including cash withdrawals).
TOTL1	Transaction type: Total transactions, excluding cash withdrawals.
CT0	Card payments (total).
EMP0	E-money payments (total).
CP0	Credit transfers (total).
DD	Direct debits.
CHQ	Cheques.
MREM	Money remittances.
SER	Payment services.
1	Payer's payment service provider (PSP).
2	Payee's payment service provider (PSP).
_Z	Payer's or payee's PSP: Not applicable.
N	Data type: Number of transactions.
PN	Unit of measure: Number (absolute).
EUR	Unit of measure: Euro.
EUR_R_POP	Unit of measure: Euro per capita.
PN_R_POP	Unit of measure: Number per capita.

Table 3.1.5 Meaning of Code in Eurosystem data

Category	Country	Category	year	Number Category	Total
Number of cheques	696	696	696	696	2,784

Total euro per capita of cheques	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total euro per capita of credit transfers	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total euro per capita of direct debits	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total euro per capita of e-money payments	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total euro per capita of other payment services	672	672	672	672	2,688
Total euro per capita of total payment transactions	672	672	672	672	2,688
Total number of card payments	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total number of credit transfers	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total number of direct debits	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total number of e-money payments	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total number of total payment transactions	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total pure number per capita of card payments	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total pure number per capita of total payment transactions	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total value of card payments	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total value of cheques	696	696	696	696	2,784

Total value of credit transfers	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total value of direct debits	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total value of e-money payments	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total value of money remittances	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total value of other payment services	696	696	696	696	2,784
Total value of total payment transactions	696	696	696	696	2,784
Value of total payment transactions	696	696	696	696	2,784
Grand Total	15,960	15,960	15,960	15,960	63,840

Table 3.1.6 Data per Category – Eurosystem

Subsegments data points

Category	card payments	cheques	cheques	credit trans	direct debits	e-money payments	money remittances	other payment services	total payment transactions	Total
Number of cheques		645								645
Total euro per capita of cheques		634								634
Total euro per capita of credit transfers				661						661
Total euro per capita of direct debits					622					622

Total euro per capita of e-money payments						191				191
Total euro per capita of other payment services								402		402
Total euro per capita of total payment transactions									216	216
Total number of card payments	662									662
Total number of credit transfers				667						667
Total number of direct debits					620					620
Total number of e-money payments						216				216
Total number of total payment transactions									665	665
Total pure number per capita of card payments	639									639
Total pure number per capita of total payment transactions									660	660
Total value of card payments	665									665

Total value of cheques		639								639
Total value of credit transfers				667						667
Total value of direct debits					629					629
Total value of e-money payments						211				211
Total value of money remittances							251			251
Total value of other payment services								480		480
Total value of total payment transactions									665	665
Value of total payment transactions									507	507
Grand Total	1,966	1,273	645	1,995	1,871	618	251	882	2,713	12,214

Table 3.1.7 Data per Subcategory – Eurosystem

4. Statistical Analysis:

4.1. Tools

To determine the tools that going to use, first is necessary to determine the size of the data sets, in this case and the raw data was divided in multiples tables but not with a large size, permitting an ease manage and storage of the information in excel. In this case “Consolidation_1” was made of around 18 datasets, “Consolidation_2” of around 20 datasets and “Consolidation_3” of 20 datasets.

The consolidations give as a result data sets with medium and small levels of data:

- ✓ Consolidation_1: 15.961 rows, 16 columns and 123.950 data points
- ✓ Consolidation_2: 531 rows, 20 columns and 3.734 data points
- ✓ Consolidation_3: 169 rows, 21 columns and 1.490 data points

A simple and widely used tool for handling this type of data is Excel. It is a versatile and user-friendly platform, widely accepted by both companies and individuals. Excel provides various functionalities, including data organization, analysis what permits depuration and normalization easier and faster appropriate for datasets of this size.

This allows users to efficiently manage the data while performing key operations such as filtering, deleting, sorting, and generating insights without requiring advanced technical knowledge.

4.2 Techniques

4.2.1 Depuration and Normalization:

To start these sections, was used excel with its different basic technics like:

Delimitation in columns: due to all columns are having a complex code as title name, it was necessary to extract from names

Transpose: To an easier manage of the information, it is decided to transpose all the data sets, for some further process but also because the periods will stay in the dates are positioned horizontally for an easier understanding.

Consolidation: it was created a consolidate database where all the transpose table.

Creating new variables: to an easier management of the information also was necessary to create variables that classify data, in this case are:

- ✓ Eurozone: where the options are yes or not.
- ✓ Cat: is the smaller definition of each row
- ✓ Number of Category: it is useful to account the categories and also to check further analysis in a fast way.
- ✓ Classification: there are 4 categories: value, number, number per capita, value to the rest of the world

4.2.2 data consistency:

.	Category.	2013.	2023.
number	Number of cheques - from Euro area	3,175	1,023
	Total number of card payments	25,281	76,029
	Total number of credit transfers	18,006	29,713
	Total number of direct debits	18,952	21,533
	Total number of e-money payments	1,783	8,908
	<u>Total number of total payment transactions</u>	<u>67,607</u>	<u>138,336</u>

Table 3.1.8 Data Consistency by Number

.	Category.	2013.	2023.
value	Total value of card payments	\$ 1,264,650	\$ 3,026,404
	Total value of cheques	\$ 3,180,488	\$ 1,148,899
	Total value of credit transfers	\$131,721,823	\$206,616,648
	Total value of direct debits	\$ 16,949,727	\$ 10,041,572
	Total value of e-money payments		\$ 495,062
	Total value of money remittances		\$ 247,605
	Total value of other payment services	\$ 1,083,559	\$ 1,049,943
	<u>Total value of total payment transactions</u>	<u>\$154,257,113</u>	<u>\$222,626,132</u>

Table 3.1.9 Data Consistency by Value

.	Category.	2013.	2023.
euro per capita	Total euro per capita of cheques	9,577	3,274
	Total euro per capita of credit transfers	396,645	588,871
	Total euro per capita of direct debits	51,040	28,619
	Total euro per capita of e-money payments		1,411
	Total euro per capita of other payment services	3,263	
	Total euro per capita of total payment transactions		637,596
	Total pure number per capita of card payments	76	217
	Total pure number per capita of total payment transactions	204	394

Table 3.1.10 Data Consistency by Euro per capita

5 Results and findings

Taking into account the characteristics of the three datasets, the analysis is divided into three chapters, primarily focusing on a numerical and value-based analysis of different financial flows.

5.1 People's Attitude

The first part of the analysis is based on the dataset 'Consolidation 2,' which contains data from a study on the attitudes of 52,180 consumers in the Eurozone. This survey provides insights into the real perceptions and behaviors of the people.

It is necessary to start here because cash transactions are not included in the statistics of the European Central Bank, as we have already said, due to the nature of this method of transfer, since there is no transactional trace here that allows for correct tracking. Therefore, understanding the behavior of cash becomes mandatory through surveys of people.

It is also important to mention that:

- ✓ This is information about the financial flows of the segment of people and not of all segments.
- ✓ The information is around the share or percentage and not about the total of transactions.

5.1.1 Payments Structure of people

Figure 5.1 Payment Structure by Number

Figure 5.2 Payment Structure by Value

As first two charts, there are information about the use case or type of technology or place of purchase or transaction that people in eurozone use during the 3 years of survey. In terms of **number** of transactions and **value** of transactions, Points of Sale (POS) are leading during the years which use methods like debit and credit card, mobile payments, cash or QR.

Despite this, **the trend** is that each year it loses more strength in number and value given the changes in the market such as online purchases which have almost doubled in just 6 years, representing 21% of the total transactions and 35% of their value, which means that the average ticket when buying in cash is the most effective, which could incur in better income and profitability for companies.

5.1.2 Digital instruments:

Now to understand the level of digitalization of people and understand the maximum level of digital payments we find the ownership of the most common digital tools.

Figure 5.3 Share of people with account 2022 vs 2024

Figure 5.4 Share of people with card 2022 vs 2024

In terms of bank account and cards ownership, we can evidence:

- ✓ High level of digitalization where practically every country exceeding 85% ownership in 2024
- ✓ Homogenization ownership across the Eurozone, reducing backlogs in countries, **bank accounts** show an increase in countries Croatia, Cyprus and Greece, while also showing a slight decline in highly digitalized nations like Netherlands or Finland and cards show an increase in Croatia, Portugal and Austria while a slight decline in Finland, Luxemburg and Cyprus

5.1.3 Online payments

As previously mentioned, online payments have shown the strongest growth among consumers in recent years, increasing rapidly across almost all countries, as illustrated in the following graph that represents the share of online payments per country versus the rest of mode of use:

Figure 5.5 Online payments by number

As can be seen, all countries except Germany show an increasing **trend** in **online** transactions, showing Germany as an outlier which also presents the least use of the platform. This partly demonstrates the adaptability that companies must have, since a quarter of the market has moved there, and the great opportunity that German companies have to attract an elusive public.

5.1.4 Methods in Online payments

Online payments rely solely on **digital methods**, eliminating cash from the equation. The **dominant methods** within online transactions are **Cards and E-payment solutions**, which consistently account for **over 70% of transactions by both number and value**. However, trends indicate **changes in payment preferences**, with some methods winning place over time.

Figure 5.6 Online payments methods by number in Eurozone

Figure 5.7 Online payments methods by value in Eurozone

✓ Number of Transactions:

- Cards remain the most used payment method, but their share has declined from 54.4% in 2019 to 48.3% in 2024, showing a gradual diversification of payment methods.
- E-payment solutions have remained stable at around 26% and 29% but haven't gained significant market share over the years.
- Direct Debits have increased slightly, rising from 3% in 2019 to 5.5% in 2024, indicating a slow but steady adoption of automatic recurring payments.

Figure 5.8 Online payments methods by number per Country

Figure 5.9 Online payments methods by value per Country

✓ Number of Transactions:

- Cards are the dominant method across most countries, with Cyprus (61%), Slovakia (56%), and Slovenia (55%) having the highest usage rates.
- E-payment solutions hold a significant share, particularly in Netherlands (76%) and Germany (46%)
- Direct debits and instant payments remain marginal in all countries.

✓ Value of Transactions:

- E-payment solutions play a key role in transaction value in the Netherlands (66%) and Germany (33%), demonstrating their importance for large payments in these economies, despite this, the share is around 10% less than the share of number indicating that people use this method for small amounts of money

- Credit transfers have a major role in high-value transactions, particularly in Austria (30%), Portugal (25%), and Estonia (31%) indicating that this method is use for big amounts of money.

5.1.5 Person to Person payments (P2P):

Figure 5.10 P2P payments methods by number in Eurozone

Figure 5.11 P2P payments methods by value in Eurozone

As far as the person-to-person relationship is concerned, cash share has lost around 40% of its financial flows in both number and monetary value,

When comparing transaction value to the number of transactions, there's a significant gap in cash flow. The total value of cash transactions is 16% lower than their share of the transaction count. This indicates that people are making higher-value purchases through digital methods,

while reserving cash for smaller transactions like purchases in coffee shops, supermarkets, restaurants or other types of stores.

Among digital methods, payment cards and mobile apps show a good relationship between the share of value and the number of transactions. However, credit transfers stand out: they account for nearly three times the value relative to their transaction volume. This suggests that credit transfers are primarily used for high-value transactions, whereas other digital options handle a more consistent range of purchase sizes.

When analyzing the trends in payment methods by value in the Euro Zone, two key patterns emerge:

- ✓ **Cards and Mobile Apps:** These have become the dominant method for daily transactions in the personal segment. Their share of the total value has significantly increased, rising from 11% in 2019 to 34% in 2024. This growth highlights the growing preference for digital payment solutions among consumers.
- ✓ **Credit Transfers:** Similarly, credit transfers have seen a substantial rise in their share of the total value, climbing from 12% in 2019 to 29% in 2024. This indicates that credit transfers remain a popular choice for higher-value transactions.

Figure 5.12 P2P payments methods by number per country

Figure 5.13 P2P payments methods by value per country

- ✓ Digital payments dominate in value, making up 76% of total P2P transactions, while cash remains frequent (41%) but represents only 24% of the total value.
- ✓ Credit transfers are the leading method for high-value transactions, particularly in Austria, Luxembourg, and Germany.
- ✓ Number of Transactions:
 - Cash is still widely used, averaging 41% across the Eurozone, but most high-value payments occur through digital methods.
 - Germany leads in cash use, followed by Lithuania and Slovakia, while France, the Netherlands, and Austria show a strong preference for digital methods.
 - Instant payments are emerging but remain secondary to credit transfers and card/mobile app transactions.
- ✓ Number of Transactions
 - Cash is still widely used, averaging 41% across the Eurozone, but most high-value payments occur through digital channels.
 - Germany leads in cash use, followed by Lithuania and Slovakia, while France, the Netherlands, and Austria show a strong preference for digital methods.
 - Instant payments are emerging but remain secondary to credit transfers and card/mobile app transactions.

5.1.6 Cash share in P2P payments:

Observing from another perspective, the next table shows us the behavior of cash as method of payment in 2024:

Figure 5.14 Share of Cash in P2P payments

- Germany is the clear outlier, with cash usage (74.1%) significantly higher than any other country in Euro Zone.
- The Netherlands has unexpectedly high cash usage (40.5%), despite leading in e-payments.
- Cash remains relevant in P2P payments but continues to decline in most countries.

5.1.7 Point of Sales (POS) payments:

Point-of-sale (POS) transactions have seen a significant shift from cash to digital payment methods between the year 2016 and the year 2024. While cash was the dominant payment method in 2016 with 78.76% of total number transaction and 53.78% of total value transaction, digital alternatives, particularly cards and mobile apps have increased considerable share in both number and value of transactions.

Figure 5.15 Share of POS payments methods by number in Eurozone

Figure 5.16 Share of POS payments methods by value in Eurozone

✓ POS Transactions by Number:

- Share of cash usage has dropped dramatically from 78.76% in 2016 to 51.62% in 2024, marking a clear shift toward digital payments.
- Cards have nearly doubled their share, increasing from 19.13% to 38.52%, showing greater adoption of credit and debit cards transactions at POS terminals.
- Mobile app payments have emerged, reaching 5.86% in 2024, highlighting the growing role of mobile wallets.

✓ POS Transactions by Value:

- Share of cash transaction value has decreased from 53.78% in 2016 to 39.22% in 2024, indicating that cash is mainly used for small amounts of money or value.
- **Cards** share now account for the largest share of value (45.30%), showing that this method is equal as other digital methods like mobile app were use for bigger amounts of transactions compared to cash.

Figure 5.17 Share of POS payments methods by number per country

Figure 5.18 Share of POS payments methods by value per country

The last two charts show the methods used in 2024, despite cash still is the main method 6 of the 20 countries in terms of number and 11 of the 20 countries in terms of value, digital methods of payment have gained participation what due to a diversification in people’s decisions.

- ✓ POS Transactions by Number:
 - The countries with the highest level of transactions in cash by values were Lithuania (59%), Slovakia (56%), and Austria (56%), suggesting a slower transition to digital payments in these markets.
 - Card payments are most prevalent in the Netherlands (56%), Finland (57%), and Luxembourg (57%), showing a clear preference for card transactions.
 - Mobile payments have gained traction, particularly in the Netherlands (19%), followed by Estonia (9%) and Luxembourg (9%).

- ✓ POS Transactions by Value:
 - Countries with the highest cash transaction values include Lithuania (59%), Slovakia (56%), and Austria (56%), suggesting a slower transition to digital payments in these markets.
 - Cards dominate in high-value transactions, with the Netherlands (63%), Finland (57%), and Luxembourg (55%) leading the shift toward card-based payments where at the same time are the lowest in the share of cash value transactions.

- ✓ The Eurozone continues its transition from cash to digital payments, but adoption rates depend on the region and depend on country. Southern, central and Eastern European nations for example still use cash frequently, while Northern and Western Europe are more digital societies accepting more methods like debit and credit cards and mobile payments, particularly for larger transactions. The Netherlands and Finland are leading the digital shift, while cash remains a major component in countries like Malta, Slovakia, and Austria.

5.2.8 Cash change 2022 - 2024

Figure 5.19 Cash change 2022 vs 2024

There is a clear tendency to reduce cash usage in almost all Eurozone countries, reinforcing the current shift toward digital payments. The data shows that most of the countries have significantly decreased their share of cash transactions at Points-of sales POS between 2022 and 2024.

The largest decrease occurred in Cyprus (-11.0%), Malta (-10.2%), Germany (-9.9%), and Portugal (-9.1%), showing a shift toward the use of digital methods of payments in these regions. Similarly, Southern and Eastern European countries, including Italy, Slovenia, Greece, Austria, and Spain, had drops between the 7% to 9%, consolidating this trend in all the eurozone with an average of -7.8%

However, Finland (+7.8%) and the Netherlands (+1.0%) stand out as exceptions, showing a reverse trend where cash usage actually increased. These two countries are among the most digital in Europe, making this shift particularly notable. This could indicate that a 100% digital society is still far from reality, as some consumers might be experiencing issues with digital payments or recognizing advantages in using cash. Possible reasons behind this increase could include:

- ✓ Consumer dissatisfaction with digital payments due to security concerns, system failures, or transaction fees.
- ✓ A preference for anonymity and better spending control with cash.

- ✓ Small businesses encourage cash payments to avoid fees associated with card transactions.

5.2 Companies Attitudes

The second part of the analysis is based on '**Consolidation 3**,' which includes data from the **Survey on the Access to Finance of Enterprises (SPACE)** performed in the fourth quarter of 2024. This survey collected responses from **7.574 enterprises** in the euro area, with a focus on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

5.2.1 Accepted and preferred means of payments

The next two charts represent payment acceptance and payment preference from the perspective of businesses in the Eurozone:

- ✓ Acceptance refers to whether companies receive payments through a particular method.
- ✓ Preference refers to the inclination businesses have toward certain payment methods when receiving money.

It is important to clarify that payment acceptance percentages are not a share as it was shown until now, unlike previous analyses where shares added up to 100%, businesses can accept multiple payment methods simultaneously, meaning the total does not sum to 100%.

Figure 5.20 Accepted means of payments in 2024 Eurozone

Figure 5.21 Preferred means of payments in 2024 Eurozone

- ✓ Card payments are widely accepted in companies with an 86% and are also the most preferred 34% (but close of preferences of cash with just a difference of 4%), showing that businesses actively encourage card usage due to its convenience and security and other possible benefits like traceability.
- ✓ Businesses accept cash with a 89%, with the highest rate than any other method but they prefer to receive it with a 30%, indicating that while they accommodate cash-paying customers, they do not necessarily favor it due to handling risks, security concerns, and operational inefficiencies.
- ✓ Mobile and online payments have a major gap—while 35% of businesses accept them, only 5% prefer receiving money through these channels.
- ✓ Bank cheques (35% acceptance) are still accommodated but are not listed as a preference, supporting the current changes about insecure and highly cost methods like it's a cheque.

5.2.2 Share of accepted and preference of cards

These two next charts represent how companies are accepting card payments and what is their preference in receiving payments via cards in the Eurozone. While card payments are widely accepted, the chart on the right reveals that not all companies actually prefer them, showing up possible concerns such as processing times, operational considerations or transaction fees that will depend on the type of contract that is impacted by the volume of

transactions in most of the times and that there is normally a fix fee where specially affect the rentability of small amounts of revenues.

Figure 5.22 Percentage of companies that prefer cards vs accept cards in 2024

- ✓ Card Acceptance by Companies in 2024: Card acceptance is extremely high across the Eurozone, with most countries exceeding 85% adoption, for example:
 - Greece (98%), Ireland (97%), and France (92%) have the highest percentage of businesses accepting cards, indicating that in these countries, card payments are nearly universal.
 - Spain, Italy, Belgium, and Malta (90%-86%) also maintain strong card acceptance rates, showing a broad shift toward digital transactions.
- ✓ Lower acceptance is seen in Eastern and Central European countries, particularly:
 - Slovakia (66%), Estonia (72%), and Lithuania (73%), where card usage is still growing but remains behind Western Europe. Germany (76%) continues to show relatively lower card acceptance, consistent with its preference for cash-based transactions in previous analyses.

5.2.3 Share of accepted and preference of cash

These two charts show how businesses in the 20 countries of the Eurozone manage cash transactions. The first chart shows the percentage of companies that accept cash, while the second chart reveals the percentage of businesses that prefer to receive payments in cash.

Figure 5.23 Percentage of companies that prefer cash vs accept cash in 2024

✓ Cash Acceptance by Companies in 2024:

- Cash remains widely accepted across the Eurozone, with most countries above 85% acceptance. Ireland (96%), France (94%), and Italy (93%) have the highest cash acceptance rates, suggesting that despite digital growth, businesses still accommodate cash-paying customers.

✓ Cash Preference by Companies in 2024:

- There is a clear gap between cash acceptance and cash preference, meaning businesses allow cash payments but do not necessarily prefer them.
- Austria (54%) stands out as the country where businesses prefer cash the most, despite having a strong digital payment infrastructure. This suggests that Austrian businesses see advantages in handling cash, such as avoiding transaction fees or faster settlement times.
- Croatia (39%), Slovenia (37%), and Italy (37%) also show a relatively high preference for cash, indicating that businesses in these countries still see value in cash transactions despite increasing digital adoption.
- Western and Northern European countries strongly prefer digital payments: The Netherlands (9%) and Finland (8%) have the lowest preference for cash, aligning with their strong adoption of card and mobile payments. France (10%) and Malta (9%) also show minimal preference for cash, despite having relatively high acceptance rates.

5.2.4 Share of accepted and preference of credit transfer

These two charts show how companies in the Eurozone manage credit transfers. The chart on the left shows the percentage of companies that **accept** credit transfers, while the chart on the right represents the percentage of businesses that **prefer** to receive payments via credit

transfers. The relationship reveals the role of bank transfers in business transactions and the differences between acceptance and preference levels.

Figure 5.24 Percentage of companies that prefer credit transfer vs accept credit transfer in 2024

- ✓ Credit Transfer Acceptance by Companies in 2024:
 - Credit transfers are widely accepted across the Eurozone, particularly in Northern and Central European countries. Estonia (96%), Lithuania (96%) Austria (90%) and Slovakia (86%) have the highest acceptance rates, reflecting a strong reliance on bank-based transactions.
 - Lower acceptance is seen in Western and Southern Europe: The Netherlands (56%), Latvia (47%), and Croatia (34%) have the lowest acceptance rates, indicating that businesses in these countries trust more on other payment methods.

- ✓ Credit Transfer preferred by Companies in 2024:
 - There is a clear gap between credit transfer acceptance and preference, meaning many businesses allow credit transfers but do not necessarily prefer them. Estonia (38%) and Lithuania (31%) have the highest preference for credit transfers, aligning with their strong digital banking infrastructure.
 - Countries with lower preference for credit transfers include France (12%), the Netherlands (10%), Ireland (7%) and Croatia (4%) showing that businesses in these regions strongly favor alternative digital payment methods, likely cards or mobile payments.

While credit transfers remain a widely accepted payment method, their preference among businesses varies significantly across the Eurozone. Northern and Central European businesses (Estonia, Lithuania, Slovakia) still prioritize bank transfers, while Western

European businesses increasingly favor digital payment alternatives like cards and mobile payments. The gap between acceptance and preference suggests that while credit transfers are a reliable payment method, many businesses prefer faster or more customer-friendly options.

5.3 Eurosystem data - European Central Bank data (all segments)

The current analysis is based on official, traceable transaction data of the European Central Bank has full access. Unlike previous datasets derived from survey-based samples of people or companies, this dataset provides a comprehensive and precise view of all recorded financial flows, this means that all transactions of all segments people, companies and government are included as is the relationship among all of the entities, this means that the data include all the financial flows C2C, C2B, C2G, B2C, B2G, B2B, G2C, G2B.

It primarily covers digital and mixed payment methods, including card payments, credit transfers, direct debits, e-money transactions, money remittances, cheques, and other forms of payment meaning that both internal and external financial flows are taken into account.

In contrast to the previous analyses, which were based on consumer and business surveys, this dataset reflects 100% of real transaction activity rather than an estimated sample, ensuring greater accuracy and a full representation of the Eurozone's payment landscape.

5.3.1 Total payment transaction

The summary of all these methods of payments bring the next two charts, total of transactions by number and Total of transactions by value.

Figure 5.25 Total number of transactions in Eurozone

✓ Total transactions by number (all segments)

Between 2019 and 2023, the total number of payment transactions in the Eurozone increased at an average rate of 8.9% per year. When this is compared with the average inflation rate of 3.58% and average GDP growth of 0.7% in the same period, this data suggests that the expansion in digital transactions has a much better performance compared with both economic growth and price inflation, what also means that financial institutions are growing at least 9 times faster than the rest of the sectors of the economy

The growth rate of financial flows in digital methods doesn't mean that the net income of financial institutions are increasing at the same level because several reasons:

- First, with higher competition there is a lower income rate. As mentioned before, there is increasing competition with neobanks.
- To attract more transactions, banks often enter into a "rate war" preferring to grow in magnitude or volume and not in rate.

This trend in number of transactions indicates that banks and financial institutions have successfully adapted to the progressing demands of the economy in terms of digitalization. The rapid acceleration in volume of transactions, despite relatively slow economic expansion, suggests an continuing shift toward digital payments and increased confidence on digital financial infrastructure that could be attributed to:

- Greater adoption of online and mobile payments by both consumers and businesses.
- Improved accessibility and efficiency of digital banking solutions.
- Accepting digital methods by consumers and businesses
- The impact of inflation, which may have led to more frequent but smaller transactions.
- The post-pandemic acceleration of digital payment methods, replacing traditional cash usage.

Figure 5.26 Total Value of Transactions in Eurozone

- ✓ Total of transactions by value (all segments)
 - Between 2019 and 2023, the total value of payment transactions in the Eurozone increased at an average rate of 8.9% per year. If 2023 is excluded, this growth rate rises to 12.7% per year. Despite a decline in 2023, an analysis of previous years shows that the increase in total transaction value is higher than the increase in the number of transactions. This indicates that digital payment methods are increasingly being used for higher-value transactions, reflecting a shift toward larger financial movements through electronic payment systems.
 - The Eurozone saw a major expansion in transaction values post-2019, followed by a recent decline in 2023, possibly due to economic slowdowns or adjustments in financial flows.

5.3.2 Payment methods by Number

These two charts show detailed information about the evolution of payment methods in the Eurozone between 2019 and 2023, focusing on both absolute transaction numbers and their respective shares. The data show the increasing dominance of card payments, the consistent presence of credit transfers and direct debits, and the growing role of e-money payments.

Figure 5.27 Payment methods in Eurozone by number

- ✓ This first chart presents the absolute number of transactions (in millions) for different payment methods each year, evidencing:
 - Card payments have grown significantly, from 46.720 million transactions in 2019 to 76.029 million in 2023, an increase of 62.7% during the 5 years confirming their dominance over all digital transactions.
 - Credit transfers have steadily increased, from 22.000 million in 2019 to 30.000 million in 2023, maintaining their relevance in larger transactions and business payments.
 - Direct debits remained stable, around 21.000 million and 23.000 million transactions per year, showing their continuous and stable role in recurring payments.
 - E-money payments saw substantial growth, from 4.625million in 2019 to 8.908 million in 2023 showing the best performance with a 92.6% of increase during the period 2019 – 2023.

Figure 5.28 Share of Payment methods in Eurozone by number

- ✓ Share of Payment Methods by Number (2019-2023):
 - Number of card payments dominate transactions, increasing from 49.35% in 2019 to 55.83% in 2023, confirming their role as the preferred consumer payment method.
 - Credit transfers have remained stable, fluctuating between 21.82% and 23.61%,
 - Direct debits have gradually declined in share, from 22.15% in 2019 to 15.81% in 2023, despite maintaining a stable absolute transaction volume.
 - E-money payments have gained traction, increasing a share from 4.89% in 2019 to 6.54% in 2023, indicating the increasing role of digital financial solutions.

5.3.3 Payment methods by value

These two charts provide visions into how payment values have changed in the Eurozone between 2019 and 2023, focusing on total value transaction and the share of each payment method. There is an a clear evidence of the dominance of credit transfers in total values but also a growing role of direct debits.

Figure 5.29 Payment methods in Eurozone by value

- ✓ Total payment value by method (2019-2023):
 - Credit transfers dominate payment values, growing over 40% from €144 trillion euros in 2019 to €207 trillion euros in 2023. It is also relevant to mention that 2022 has been the year with the highest financial flows levels and 2023 experienced a correction possibly influenced by economic stabilization and external factors.
 - Direct debits show continuous growth, rising from €7 trillion euros in 2019 to €10 trillion euros in 2023, emphasizing their continued use for recurring payments such as utility bills, loans, and subscriptions for example to insurance, gym or others.
 - The rest of the digital methods represent less than 3%, which is not vastly relevant in terms of value.

Figure 5.30 Share of Payment methods in Eurozone by value

- ✓ Share of Payment Methods by Number (2019-2023):
 - Credit transfers consistently account for over 90% of total transaction value, topping at 94.01% in 2022 before slightly decreasing to 92.81% in 2023. This suggests that there is a slow diversification in total payment preferences by value.
 - 2022 was an exceptional year, with the highest share of credit transfers (94.01%) and overall transaction value, followed by a decline in 2023. This aligns with economic stabilization, reduced financial liquidity, and central bank policies to combat inflation.

5.3.4 Total transactions per capita

These two charts show information about per capita payment behaviors across Eurozone countries, analyzing both the number of transactions and the value of transactions per person. This will help us to understand better the level of digitalization per person due to the information of total transactions is divided by the population of each country.

This also help to reduce bias that could exist if the analysis is made only by a hole country for the reason that the size of the economy of Germany is multiple times larger than the economy of Lithuania for example, and this point of view permit us see the behavior as a one.

Figure 5.31 Total number of transactions per capita

- ✓ Transactions per capita by Number:
 - Luxembourg has the first position where each person does more transactions, with an increase from 5,471 transactions per capita in 2019 to 9,011 in 2023, far surpassing other countries. This reflects Luxembourg's role as a financial hub with high corporate transaction volumes. This is also not as surprising due to the GDP per capita of Luxembourg was the highest of euro zone in 2023 with \$125,841 USD, allowing to have a great purchasing power which in turn allows to carry out a greater number of transactions
 - Lithuania, Ireland, Netherland and Finland also perform well, with per capita transactions ranging between 600 and 1.134 per person, showing high digitalization and extensive electronic payment usage.
 - Larger economies like Germany and France have moderate per capita transactions, Germany with 342 and France with 448 for 2023 suggesting a considerable limited confidence on digital methods that has important use in higher-value transactions but not in small-value transactions and having preference for alternative payment methods like cash Going in the same direction as previous analyses where the preference for cash is evident, especially on the part of Germany.
 - Southern and Eastern European countries like Greece, Italy Croatia and Estonia remain at the end, with per capita transactions between 200-300, reflecting slower digital payment adoption.

Figure 5.32 Total value of transactions per capita

- ✓ Transactions per capita by Value:
 - Luxembourg again leads the chart, though it experienced a decline from €6 million per capita in 2019 to €5.5 million in 2023. Despite the drop, the country remains an outlier due to the gap that exists with the rest of the countries.
 - Netherlands increase from €1.1 million to €3.1million per capita and Ireland: from €0.8M to €1.9M per capita reflecting high-value transactions likely driven by its strong tech and financial sectors. These two countries are also not a surprise due to the GDP per capita are the two highest after Luxemburg in the eurozone, Ireland with \$106,623 USD and Netherlands with \$80,195
 - Southern and Eastern European countries like Greece, Croatia, Estonia) stay below €0.2M per capita, highlighting lower transaction values per person, likely due to smaller economies and lower digital payment penetration.

5.3.5 Total payments transactions per country by value

These two charts compare the total payment transaction values in 2019 and 2023 across the 20 Eurozone countries.

Figure 5.33 Total payment transaction by value per country - top 10

Figure 5.34 Total payment transaction by value per country - bottom 10

- As is expected Germany take the lead in the Eurozone in total transaction value, increasing from €59 trillion euros in 2019 to €70 trillion euros in 2023, reflecting its continued dominance in economic activity and financial transactions.
- The Netherlands experienced a really high increase, rising from €20 trillion euros in 2019 to €56 trillion euros in 2023, indicating a fast digital payment adoption and a shift towards high-value transactions.

It is important to mention that Netherland despite being the fifth largest country in terms of population with around 18 million of inhabitants in 2023, is the second largest economy in terms of total transactions by value (Germany has 4.6 times the population of Netherlands, France 3.8 times, Italy 3.2 times and Spain 2.7 times)

- France also had a notable growth of 4 trillion euros in the same period, from €29 trillion euros to €33 trillion euros.

- Smaller economies, such as Lithuania and Ireland increase their value of transactions more than doubled having the best performance between 2019 and 2023, showing the fastest increasing in digitalization and economic activity in all eurozone.
- Some countries, such as Spain, Portugal, and Luxembourg, had no change during this period, which in the case of Luxembourg is due to a possible very high level of digitalization reaching the edge of digitalization and in the case of Spain and Portugal a slowdown in adoption.

5.4.1 Total payments transactions per country by number

These two charts compare the total number of payment transactions in 2019 and 2023 through the 20 countries of Eurozone. The data shows an increase in digital transactions in all the countries, with Western European countries leading in volume and Eastern European countries experiencing the fastest growth rates.

Figure 5.35 Total payment transactions by Number- top 10

Figure 5.36 Total payment transactions by Number- bottom 10

- France and Germany lead the Eurozone in total transactions, France with an increasing from 25.000 thousand to 31.000 thousand transactions and Germany with

an increase from 24.000 million to 29.000 million transactions between 2019 and 2023. This make evident that despite Germany is the first economy with a difference of more 1 trillion USD with France, is this last, the country with the greatest number of transactions.

Here is important to mention that Germany and France are the biggest economies of euro zone respectively. The first with 4.456 trillion USD, accounting for 4.23% of the global economy and the second, France's GDP reached approximately \$3.031 trillion USD, representing 2.87% of the world economy (Trading Economics, 2023).

- Spain showed significant growth, starting from 9.000 million to 15.000 million of transactions, indicating grew on the adoption of digital and contactless payments.
- The Netherlands and Italy also experienced notable increases, reaching 13.000 million transactions each in 2023, indicating a shift towards more frequent transactions, likely to e-commerce and mobile payments.
- Smaller economies, such as Luxembourg and Finland, doubled their transaction numbers, highlighting growing digital adoption in countries that historically relied on traditional banking.

5.4.2 Top 10 countries by credit transfer

The two bar charts illustrate the top 10 countries by credit transfer number and credit transfer value from 2019 to 2023. This analysis start with credit transfer because how it was shown before, this is the most important method representing a 92.81% of share value for 2023 and 21.82% of share number

Figure 5.37 Top 10 countries by credit transfer number

Figure 5.38 Top 10 countries by credit transfer value

✓ Credit transfer by number:

- As it was expected Germany leads with the highest number of transactions, growing from 6.700 million (2019) to 7.300 million (2023).
- France and Netherlands follow, showing continuous growth excepting 2023 year where there is an adjustment. France increased from 4.300 million of transactions to 5.600 million of transactions, while the Netherlands rose from 2.800 million of transactions to 4.100 million of transactions.
- Spain, Belgium, and Italy saw moderate growth, with Italy reaching 2.100 million transactions in 2023.
- Countries like Finland, Austria, Ireland, and Greece had lower transaction volumes but still showed a slight upward trend.

✓ Credit transfer by value:

- Germany maintains the top position in transaction value, increasing from €55 trillion in 2019 to €64trillion in 2023, reflecting its dominance in high-value flows
- The Netherlands shows a dramatic rise in transaction value, jumping from €19 trillion in 2019 to €55 trillion in 2022, before slightly decreasing to €50 trillion in 2023. This emphasizes high-value transactions despite the recent decline, additionally the comportment of Netherlands in terms of value has been unusual between the period from 2019 to 2023, its growth rate of more than 180% has been extremely high

5.4.3 Top 10 countries by direct debits

Continuing with the second most important method in terms of value, These two charts present a comparative analysis of **direct debit** transactions across the top 10 Eurozone countries over the period 2019-2023, focusing on both the number of transactions and their total value

Figure 5.39 Top 10 countries by direct debits number

✓ Direct Debit by number:

- Germany leads significantly in direct debit usage, though the number of transactions decreased from 10.700 million of transactions in 2019 to 9.400 million of transactions in 2023.
- France holds a strong second position, growing from 4.4K million to 4.6K million transactions, showing consistent usage of direct debits for recurring payments.
- Spain and the Netherlands follow, with Spain growing modestly from 2.0K to 2.2K million transactions and the Netherlands increasing from 1.5K to 2.3K million in 2023, indicating strong adoption of automated payments.

Figure 5.40 Top 10 countries by direct debits value

✓ Direct Debit by value:

- Germany leads not only in volume but also in value, with transaction values increasing from €3.4 trillion euros in 2019 to €5.4 trillion euros in 2023, despite the decline in transaction count. This suggests a shift towards higher-value direct debits, potentially for business or government-related payments.
- France shows constant growth, from €1.7 trillion euros to €2.1 trillion euros, aligning with the gradual increase in transaction volume.
- Spain, Italy, Netherlands and Austria show consistent values from €0.2 trillion to €0.7 trillion euros, despite modest changes in transaction numbers, indicating stability in recurring payment habits.
- The rest of the countries represent less than €0.1 trillion euros, not representing more than 1% of total of direct debits transactions.

5.3.8 Top 10 countries by cards

The following analysis explores the evolution of card payments in the top 10 Eurozone countries, focusing on the number of debit cards and credit card payment transactions and their total value between 2019 and 2023. The data show up, adoption and growth trends in card usage across different economies.

Figure 5.41 Top 10 countries by card payments number

✓ Cards by number:

- France leads Card payment transactions by a wide margin, with transactions growing from 14.600 million in 2019 to 19.4000 million in 2023, this represents a difference with the second country of more than 7.000 million of transactions, a similar level of transactions of the fourth

most important country in terms of cards number of transactions, Netherlands.

- Germany follows with significant growth over the 80% from 6.300 million transactions to 11.800 million transactions, indicating a quick shift towards card payments, despite the country’s historical preference for cash and bank transfers.
- Spain and the Netherlands show consistent growth, with Spain rising from 5.100 to 10.400 million transactions, and the Netherlands increasing from 5.500 to 6.300 million, reflecting constant adoption of card payments.
- Italy shows one of the fastest growth around 90%, with card payments increasing from 3.800 million to 7.200 million transactions, showing up strong consumer adoption in recent years.
- Belgium and Portugal saw moderate increases, with Belgium growing from 2.300 million to 3.600 million and Portugal from 1.700 million to 2.500 million transactions.
- Ireland, Greece, and Lithuania despite represent smaller markets, have important growth rate but still showed significant relative growth: Ireland with 225% from 0.800 million to 2.600 million, Lithuania with 500% from 0.400 million to 2.500 million and Greece with 400% from 0.400 million to 2.000 million

Figure 5.42 Top 10 countries by card payments value

✓ Cards by value:

- France leads in card payment value, increasing from €0.61trillion euros in 2019 to €0.81trillion euros in 2023, what is in the same line of leadership transaction volume.

- Germany follows, growing from €0.35 trillion euros to €0.55 trillion euros, showing that the surge in transaction numbers is also reflected in the overall payment value.
- The rest of the countries remains a constant growth and in general exist a slower growth of value transactions compare with the growth of number of transactions, what means that despite the important growth in both categories, this is based specially based on small-value transactions letting high-value transactions to other digital methods.

5.3.10 Top 10 countries by e-money

This chart highlights the evolution of e-money payment values across the top 10 Eurozone countries between 2019 and 2023. E-money payments typically include digital wallets, prepaid cards, and mobile payment solutions.

Figure 5.43 Top 10 countries by e-money value

- Luxembourg dominates the e-money payment market, with values increasing from €0.14 trillion euros in 2019 to €0.28 trillion euros in 2023. The country's financial services sector and high-income population are likely to contribute to this substantial adoption of e-money solutions.
- Unlike what was expected from the information coming from the two previous analyses of surveys of people and companies, e-wallet still represents a small percentage of the total but with great potential for growth given the preferences that people have been taking towards this method.

5.3.11 Top 10 countries by other payments services

This chart highlights the total value of "other payment services" across the top 10 Eurozone countries from 2019 to 2023.

Figure 5.44 Top 10 countries by other payments services value

- Italy leads the category of "other payment services" by a significant margin, with the value growing from €0.58 trillion euros in 2019 to €0.74 trillion euros in 2023 with a growth rate of 18.9% during the 5 years or a growth lower to 4% yearly. This growth indicates that despite the increasing usage of alternative payment methods, it is not relevant in terms of volume compared to other methods.
- Germany follows, though with lower values compared to Italy. The total declined from €0.53 trillion euros in 2019 to €0.40 trillion euros in 2023, suggesting a gradual reduction in the use of alternative payment methods.
- Spain holds the third position, though with a much lower value, decreasing from €0.26 trillion euros to €0.06 trillion euros over the period.
- This decline in almost all countries indicate the limited competitive that other payment services have compare to previous methods mentioned.

5.3.12 Top 10 countries by cheques

Figure 5.45 Top 10 countries by cheques value

- Italy leads the chart in cheque usage by value, although there is a clear decreasing trend. Cheque values decreased from €0.38 trillion euros in 2019 to €0.25 trillion euros in 2023, indicating a gradual preference for other digital methods.

- Spain follows closely, with cheque values also decreasing from €0.28 trillion euros to €0.18 trillion euros over the same period. This decline illustrates a trend seen across Europe, where digital alternatives are increasingly favored.
- Overall, there is a clear trend of declining cheque usage across all countries, as is reflected in the decreasing transaction values. This decline can be attributed, in part, to the high costs and inefficiency associated with cheques compared to more modern digital payment methods.

5.4 Clustering of Countries Based on Point of Sale (POS) transactions

The following analysis aims to determine whether the countries of the Eurozone exhibit distinct or similar behaviors in Point of Sale (POS) transactions to create appropriate clustering. POS transactions were chosen because they reflect daily consumer spending habits, like going to the supermarket, pharmacy, hospital or a simple restaurant. By analyzing POS transactions, we can understand better how the countries' conducts are.

This clustering analysis is made using the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) machine learning method. The optimal number of clusters is determined using the Elbow Method and the Silhouette Method, ensuring that the chosen classification structure effectively represents the patterns observed in the data. These methods help identify the most meaningful way to segment Eurozone countries based on their POS transaction behavior.

5.4.1 Elbow method:

Figure 5.46 Elbow method

In the case of the Elbow Method, the chosen point is typically the point of inflection, where the curve changes concavity. In this case, the method identifies a point of inflection between 2 and 4, with a higher probability of 2 due to the steeper slope. However, this result is not entirely clear, so a second method is used to confirm the optimal number of clusters

5.4.1 Silhouette Method

Figure 5.47 Silhouette Method

In this case, the Silhouette method estimates that the optimal number of clusters (K) is 2, where the silhouette score is the highest, this also showed that more clusters reduce the clustering quality. As a final decision, 2 clusters are chosen showing that indeed there are differences between the countries of the eurozone in terms of digitalization.

5.4.2 K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) = 2

As it was shown, the main conclusion is that there are 2 clusters where the countries can be classified, the next scatter plot shows the classification of Eurozone countries based on the number of payment made Point of Sale (POS) in 2024 showing a cluster (in green) where there is an important level of digital adoption methods like payments made by mobile apps, credit cards, debit cards, and other digital payments but also a cluster (in red) where countries have higher tendency of Physical Methods in this case Cash or lower digital adoption, while the y-axis represents Digital Methods.

Figure 5.48 Classification KNN

The plot groups countries into two clusters

Cluster 0 (Blue Dots) → Countries with a higher reliance on physical (cash) transactions.

Cluster 1 (Green Dots) → Countries that prefer digital payment methods.

in the chart, there is a tendency where western and northern countries are more likely to have higher digital adoption like Netherlands, Finland, Luxembourg, Estonia, Belgium, France and Latvia and countries of the mediterranean and central Europe have low level of digital adoptions methods to make any transaction showing and supporting similar analysis made before.

However, the gap is gradually closing. With the European Union pushing for a cashless economy, increased adoption of mobile wallets, instant payments, and fintech innovations is expected to accelerate digital payment growth even in cash-heavy economies

5.5 Predictions of Total transactions in terms of number and value

5.5.1 Predictions of total transactions in terms of number

In terms of predictions, this is made based on the total number of transactions due to is the summarization of all digital methods and mix methods (credit transfer, direct debits, credit cards, debit cards, e-money payments and cheques). This is done with the objective of

showing the continuous potential market for banking sectors, companies and people and let them create strategies to generate better results.

Figure 5.49 Prediction of total payments by number

In the last chart, it shows a prediction for the number of payments transactions for 2030 of 200.000 million of transactions, it means more than 60.000 million of transactions compared to 2023, an average growth rate over 6% per year, assuming a steady increase.

The gray-shaded area represents the confidence interval, meaning that while 210 billion is the central prediction, actual transactions could be higher or lower depending on economic, technological, and regulatory factors.

4.2.2 Predictions of total transactions in terms of value

Figure 5.50 Prediction of total payments by value

Looking ahead, the prediction model (represented by the dashed line and shaded confidence interval) projects continued growth in transaction value, reaching approximately €223 trillion euros by 2025, with an increase approaching to €290 Trillion by 2030. The confidence interval expands, indicating higher uncertainty in long-term forecasts. This suggests that

while digital payment adoption is expected to increase, external economic factors, regulatory changes, or technological advancements could influence the final trajectory. Understanding these trends is essential for banks, financial institutions, and businesses to strategize investment and digital payment innovations accordingly.

6. Discussion

1. **People's Attitudes:** The data from SPACE survey based on consumer attitudes reveal a significant shift in behaviors of the people around payments methods in all the twenty (20) countries of Eurozone. While cash continues being a widely used payment method, especially in countries like Germany, there is a clear change around the preference of people, letting a higher diversification of methods that are basically digital methods of payments. The use of cash had a decline in both in point-of-sale (POS) and Person to Person transactions (P2P) , with a decrease in number of transactions of 27.16% falling from 78.76% in 2016 to 51.62% in 2024 for POS and a decrease of 45.37% falling from 86% to 40.63%, a behavior that is contrary in digital methods of payments.

Despite the growth in digital adoption in the different scenarios (POS and P2P), cash remains as the most important method of payment in some countries. Germany, for instance, continues to show a strong preference for cash, showed in high cash usage rates in P2P and POS payments, indicating that the growth in the use of different digital payment methods is disproportionate across all countries.

Another critical issue is the growing importance of online payments, which have nearly doubled in usage, representing 21.21% of the number of transactions for 2024 and 35% of their value, reflecting a fast change in consumers preference around e-commerce and digital payment platforms.

In other point of view of digital adoption, the ownership of digital tools like bank accounts and cards has become nearly universal across the Eurozone, with most countries exceeding 85% penetration. However, there are still gaps in digital adoption and accessibility, particularly among older populations and in countries with lower GDP per capita.

2. **Companies' Attitudes:** Companies in the Eurozone have generally accepted digital payments, but there are notable disparities in their preferences and acceptance. For example, Card payments are widely accepted with 86% and are the most preferred method with 34% due to their convenience and security. However, cash acceptance remains higher at 89%, but the preference is of 30% being on the second position, likely due to operational inefficiencies and security concerns.

There is a visible difference between the payment methods that companies accept and the payments methods that they prefer. For instance, while 35% of companies accept mobile and online payments, only 5% prefer them, showing resistance and possibly concerns over fees or low interest of the people preferences.

The data also shows that companies are adapting to consumer preferences, particularly in countries where digital adoption is high like the Netherlands and Finland where businesses are leading the shift to digital payments, with high acceptance rates for cards and mobile payments. In contrast, in Southern and Eastern Europe, businesses still are on cash transactions, reflecting slower digital adoption in these regions.

3. European Central Bank Data: The ECB data confirms the trends observed in the data of all segments. Between 2019 and 2023, there was a significant increase in the total number of digital payment transactions, with an average annual growth rate of 8.9%. Card payments saw the highest growth, increasing by 62.7% in the five years, while e-money payments grew by an impressive 92.6%, albeit from a smaller base.

Credit transfers control total transactions by value during all periods, with a share over 90% of total value, peaking at 94.01% in 2022. This shows the role of credit transfer in high-value transactions despite that card payments are the method of most use in terms of number of transactions.

However, the constant increase, 2023 saw a slight decline in transaction by value, likely due to economic correction and reduced financial liquidity. Despite this, the overall trend indicates increasing adoption on digital payment methods, with gradual diversification.

4. Clustering of Countries Based on Point of Sale (POS) transactions

This analysis examines POS transactions to identify distinct payment behaviors among Eurozone countries. POS transactions reflect daily consumer spending and provide insights into digital payment adoption. Using K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and optimizing with the Elbow and Silhouette Methods, two clusters were identified:

Cluster 0 (Blue Dots) → Higher reliance on cash transactions.

Cluster 1 (Green Dots) → Strong digital payment adoption.

Key Findings

Western and Northern Europe (Netherlands, Finland, Luxembourg, Estonia, Belgium, France, Latvia) have the best performance in digital transactions due to advanced financial infrastructure and fintech adoption.

Mediterranean & Central Europe (Italy, Austria, Slovenia, Malta, Portugal, Spain, Greece, parts of Germany) rely more on cash, influenced by cultural habits, informal economies.

5. Predictions of Total transactions in terms of number and value

- Transaction Volume

By 2030, the total number of transactions is projected to reach 200 billion, a 60 billion increase from 2023, with an average growth rate of over 6% per year. The prediction also suggests variations depending on economic conditions, technology, and regulations.

- Transaction Value

Total transaction value is expected to hit €223 trillion by 2025 and €290 trillion by 2030. Long-term uncertainty exists due to economic and technological shifts, but the trend points to a continued rise in digital payments.

Eurozone countries show clear regional differences in payment behavior, but digitalization is increasing. Predictions indicate significant growth in digital transactions, requiring financial institutions, regulators, and businesses to adapt and innovate to meet evolving consumer needs.

7. Conclusion

The analysis of financial flows in the Eurozone shows a clear diversification of methods of payments, especially facing a shift to digital payment methods, which are thanks to technological advancements and changing in consumer preferences. However, challenges are still present to achieve a maybe “utopic” 100% digital economy. The following key points summarize the findings and provide actionable recommendations:

7.1. Diversification of Payment Methods and Decline of Cash

Cash usage is reducing the participation as a method of payment in almost all countries of Eurozone, particularly in scenarios of point-of-sale (POS) and person-to-person (P2P), but this method is still the main method in countries like Germany and Southern Europe due in part to the rejection that people have towards digital issues this is despite the existence of the infrastructure for such a change.

The prediction models confirm this diversification, projecting a continuous rise in the number and value of digital transactions, reinforcing the shift toward digital adoption.

To accelerate the transition, governments and financial institutions should focus on improving digital payment accessibility and adoption, especially for older populations and regions with slower adoption rates.

7.2 Credit Transfers Dominate High-Value Transactions, while Card Payments Drive Small-Value Transactions

Credit transfers represent for over 90% of value transactions thanks to possible high value transactions made in part for big companies and government. Since as it was observed, people have a greater preference for other methods such as cards or cash., accentuating their importance in business and government payments. Meanwhile, card payments have seen significant growth, particularly for small-value transactions, reflecting consumer preference for contactless and mobile payment solutions.

Businesses and financial institutions should continue to innovate in card payment technologies, offering competitive fees and unified integration with e-commerce platforms to meet growing demand.

7.3 Regional Disparities in Digital Adoption

The analysis shows a significant regional disparity in digital payment methods. Northern and Western European countries, such as the Netherlands and Finland, are the countries with best performance in the digital shift, while Southern and Eastern European countries present a relative lag, showing a heterogenic adoption, this is reinforced by the KKN model that show that the eurozone can be divided in two main groups, western and northern countries are more likely to have higher digital adoption like Netherlands, Finland, Luxemburg, Estonia, Belgium, France and Latvia and countries of the mediterranean and central Europe have low level of digital adoptions methods.

To reduce these disparities, is necessary create initiatives to promote digital payment adoption in regions with lower GDP per capita and slower digitalization rates. This could include financial incentives for businesses to adopt digital payment methods, public awareness campaigns, and investments in digital infrastructure.

The Eurozone is having a transformation to a diversified payment ecosystem specially based on digital methods, but the persistence of cash and regional disparities highlight the need for continued collaboration among policymakers, businesses, and financial institutions. By fostering innovation, promoting financial inclusion, and addressing barriers to digital adoption, the Eurozone can build a resilient and dynamic payment system that supports economic growth and enhances the financial well-being of its citizens.

8. Appendix

8.1 General terms

Clients: A client is an individual, business or organization that holds a formal relationship with the bank, this means that have done the enrollment with all personal or private information to identify the client, this also comes typically involving financial agreements, products, or services.

Economies of market: “economies rely on the payment system to facilitate trade and exchange among firms and consumers in product markets.”(Hancock and Humphrey, 1997)

Financial system: A financial system is a set of institutions, such as banks, insurance companies, and stock exchanges, that permit the exchange of funds. (*Financial Terms Dictionary*, 2024)

Monetary system: the system used by a country to provide money and to control the exchange of money (Cambridge English Dictionary, 2025)

Financial transaction: A transaction is a completed agreement between a buyer and a seller to exchange goods, services, or financial assets in return for money (*Financial Terms Dictionary*, 2024)

Traditional banking: is characterized by physical locations where customers can visit to access financial services and interact with staff members in person. Including a registered headquarters, and a strict Government license to operate in the state or country (Transfy, 2025)

Users: A user is someone who interacts with the bank's services, digital or physical, but may not necessarily be the legal account holder or primary client, this limited the services or products that the user can do, and just can do basic things that don't incur in risk the bank like payment of bills or simple transactions to accounts of clients for example.

Revaluation: the act of calculating the value of something again, especially to give it a higher value than before (Cambridge English Dictionary, 2025)

Devaluation: Devaluation, the deliberate downward adjustment in the official exchange rate, reduces the currency's value; in contrast, a revaluation is an upward change in the currency's value. (International Monetary Forum, no date)

Payment Network Franchises: A payment network is a system that connects financial institutions to facilitate the transfer of funds between banks, allowing for the transmission of payment messages and transactions (ScienceDirect, 2020)

Neobanks: are financial technology companies that offer digital banking products and services through websites or mobile apps. They aim to disrupt traditional banking models by offering competitive rates on loans, low fees, and higher-than-average interest rates on deposit accounts. (*Financial Terms Dictionary*, 2024)

Cash: Banknotes and coins that are carried out at the time and in person

Mixed Methods: Payment methods that combine both physical and digital processes. For example, services like Western Union, where the payer physically brings cash to a location, and the funds are then transferred digitally to the recipient's account or made available for physical withdraw.

Cheques: A written order from one party (the drawer) to another (the drawee; normally a credit institution) requiring the drawee to pay a specified sum on demand to the drawer or a third party specified by the drawer.

Remittances: an amount of money that a person send to someone outside of the country (Cambridge English Dictionary, 2025)

and particularly digital methods such:

Credit transfer: A payment method where a payer instructs their payment service provider (e.g., a bank) to transfer funds directly to a beneficiary's account. (*Credit transfers | ECB Data Portal*, 2025)

Direct Debits: A payment that occurs when someone let a company take money directly from his or her bank account to pay for things like bills, subscriptions, or for example the insurance. (Bank, 2024)

E-money: An electronic store of monetary value on a technical device that may be widely used for making payments to entities other than the e-money issuer (*Electronic money | ECB Data Portal*, 2025)

Credit and debit card: A payment through a usage of a debit or credit card to pay for something, whether in a store, online, or at a mobile POS (Point of sale) (Bank, 2019)

8.2 Transactions from a banking perspective

Financial flows in daily life versus banking: in daily life financial flows can be also associated with payments and transactions, but name a financial flow depending of the point of view that this is made, it could be also named as receiving or collection of payments and transactions, all this will depend the position of sender or receiver.

Payments, from a banking perspective, refer to regulated and fully identifiable cash flows from the origin to the end. Examples include salary payments or payments of taxes where the amount, the sender, the recipient, and the payment deadline are clearly defined. In contrast, transactions are more flexible and less structured. They involve the transfer of funds that may not follow a predefined schedule or specific criteria, while in a transaction these exact data do not exist but it is a transfer that can be made freely by the person sending the money at any time, whether because a service is provided or not or a product is purchased or sold.

8.3 Model to determine KNN

```
9. from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, confusion_matrix
from sklearn.decomposition import PCA
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score
from adjustText import adjust_text

# Excel Location
file_path =
r"C:\Users\ASUS\Downloads\Thesis\base_Machine_learning.xlsx"

# read sheet "POS" from Excel
df = pd.read_excel(file_path, sheet_name="POS")

# Normalization of data deleting spaces of the names
df.columns = df.columns.str.strip()

# Verifying that columns are well
print("Columnas disponibles:")
print(df.columns)

# Filter only "number" and year 2024
df_pos_number = df[(df["Metric"] == "number") & (df["year"] == 2024)]

# Verify if the filter bring back data
if df_pos_number.empty:
    print("\n;Attention! there is not data, verify.")
else:
    print("\nFilter Data:")
    print(df_pos_number)

# Select the columns for clustering
try:
    X = df_pos_number[["Cash", "Cards", "Mobile_app", "Other"]]
except KeyError as e:
```

```

        print(f"\nError: {e}")
        print("verify columns 'Cash', 'Cards', 'Mobile_app', and
'Other' exist.")
        exit()

# Elbow Method
wcss = []
for k in range(1, 11):
    kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=k, random_state=42)
    kmeans.fit(X)
    wcss.append(kmeans.inertia_)

# Elbow Method
plt.plot(range(1, 11), wcss, marker='o')
plt.xlabel('Number of clusters (k)')
plt.ylabel('WCSS')
plt.title('Elbow Method POS payments')
plt.show()

# Silhouette Method
silhouette_scores = []
for k in range(2, 11):
    kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=k, random_state=42)
    kmeans.fit(X)
    score = silhouette_score(X, kmeans.labels_)
    silhouette_scores.append(score)

# Plot Silhouette Score
plt.plot(range(2, 11), silhouette_scores, marker='o')
plt.xlabel('Number of clusters (k)')
plt.ylabel('Silhouette Score')
plt.title('Silhouette Method POS payments')
plt.show()

# Create a column for summarize of digital methods (Cards + Mobile app
+ Other)
df_pos_number["Digital"] = df_pos_number["Cards"] +
df_pos_number["Mobile_app"] + df_pos_number["Other"]

# Now there are 2 main columns
X = df_pos_number[["Cash", "Digital"]]

# According to elbow and silhouette models k=2 is the best fitting
kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=2, random_state=42)
kmeans.fit(X)

# country vs cluster
df_pos_number["Cluster"] = kmeans.labels_

# plot cluster
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))

# Colors for plot
colors = ["blue", "green"]

# Graph every country and its cluster
for i, cluster in enumerate(df_pos_number["Cluster"]):
    plt.scatter(X.iloc[i, 0], X.iloc[i, 1], color=colors[cluster],
label=f"Cluster {cluster}")

# list to add all the label to text

```

```

texts = []

# add labels to data points
for i, country in enumerate(df_pos_number["Region"]):
    texts.append(plt.text(X.iloc[i, 0], X.iloc[i, 1], country,
        fontsize=9))
# Adjust text
adjust_text(texts)

plt.xlabel("Physical Methods (Cash)")
plt.ylabel("Digital Methods")
plt.title("Classification of Countries according to number of POS
payments 2024")

handles, labels = plt.gca().get_legend_handles_labels()
by_label = dict(zip(labels, handles)) # Remove duplicates
plt.legend(by_label.values(), by_label.keys(), bbox_to_anchor=(0.5, -
0.1), loc='upper center', ncol=2)

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

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